

THE ROLE OF THE MEDIA IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SPEECH CULTURE

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Anvarova Dilobar Doniyor qizi

Tashkent State University of Uzbek Language and Literature named after Alisher Navo'i

Abstract: Language and society are closely related to each other. Just as there can be no language outside of society, so society cannot exist without language. Their influence on each other is mutual.

The culture of speech is an indicator of the culture of both an individual and the whole society as a whole. The more careful the attitude towards the cultural heritage accumulated by mankind, including the attitude towards the language, the longer the national culture will be preserved.

The culture of speech in the media is one of the main characteristics that determine the professional level of television and radio programs, their journalistic and artistic usefulness. Most often, “forgetfulness”, according to the authors of the letter, announcers and presenters about the need for the correct pronunciation of words, happens due to the general low culture of speaking.

In not so distant times, on Central Television and All-Union Radio, the culture of speech of announcers and presenters was strictly treated, there was control over speech on the air and a well-thought-out system for improving language skills. Today, unfortunately, much has been lost in this important matter - only certain TV and radio channels are taking measures to somehow prevent speech errors of announcers.

The mass media (hereinafter referred to as the media) are divided into visual (periodical) press, audio (radio), audiovisual (television, documentaries). Despite all the differences between them, the media are united into a single system of mass communication due to the commonality of functions and the special structure of the communication process.

Among the functions of the media, the following are usually distinguished:
informational (message about the state of affairs, various facts and events);
commentary-evaluative (often the statement of facts is accompanied by a commentary on them, their analysis and evaluation);
cognitive and educational (transmitting diverse cultural, historical, scientific information, the media contributes to the replenishment of the knowledge fund of its readers, listeners, viewers);

the function of influence (it is no coincidence that the media is called the “fourth estate”: their influence on the views and behavior of people is obvious, especially during

periods of so-called inversion changes in society or during mass socio-political actions, for example, during the general election of the head of state);

The development of the media, the pace and nature of their growth, the process of their transformation in the context of the country's transition to a market economy and the democratization of the political system - all this should be considered as the reason for the influence on the process of forming the language of electronic media, since these shocks had a direct impact on the process of deformation language.

The language of the media plays an important role both in the spread of the language and in raising the literacy of the population. And although there are some positive results of the work of the media on the formation of a respectful attitude towards the language. Considering the attitude of young people to television – for many it is the only source and “beacon” in life – the media should carefully handle the language.

The abolition of censorship led to the appearance of spontaneous oral speech on the air, democratization - to the participation in public communication of persons with different education and the level of speech culture.

Hedonistic (we are talking here not just about entertaining information, but also about the fact that any information is perceived with a great positive effect, when the very way it is transmitted causes a feeling of pleasure, meets the aesthetic needs of the addressee).

The media are also united as a special type of communication, which can be characterized as distant, real (transmission of a message to an unknown and quantified recipient of information), with an individual-collective subject (this means not only co-authorship, but also, for example, the common position of a newspaper, television or radio channel) and a mass dispersed addressee.

The differences between the media are based, first of all, on the difference between the codes used in them, the sign complexes.

The periodical press presents a binary sign system: natural language in its printed form, plus iconic signs (photos, drawings, cartoons) that plays an auxiliary role, as well as various types of font selections, layout methods, etc.

With regard to radio, we can talk about a triad: oral speech plus natural sounds (noises) and music. In audiovisual media (TV, documentary film), the triad is transformed into a tetrad as a result of the emergence of such an important way for these media to transmit information and influence the audience as a “live” image.

The media largely determine the norms of language and communication, and their responsibility is even greater for ensuring that these norms correspond to the best cultural traditions. The periodical press, the most traditional type of mass media, remains today the most important mass media, which has a significant potential for influencing not only the reader, but also various aspects of society.

Leafing through any periodical, the reader often begins to get acquainted with the newspaper from the headlines, so the phrases containing them are graphically highlighted and the reader notices them before other turns of speech. There are many means of speech expressiveness, with the help of which a journalist tries to attract the reader's attention, placing logical accents and experimenting with language.

One of the brightest and most interesting means of speech expression used in journalism is allusion.

Allusion is a method of text formation, which consists in correlating the created text with some precedent fact - literary or historical.

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